

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SECURITY UNIT IN PERFORMING ON TASK AND ROLE – BASED ON PERPOL NO. 4 / 2020 IN SURABAYA CITY

Theodorus Warman¹, Arief Darmawan², Rachmawati Novaria³
Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, University of 17 August 1945 Surabaya
theowarmanbumimoro72marinir@gmail.com

Abstract

One of the requirements that foreign parties consider to invest in Indonesia is the security factor. To maintain the security of the Republic of Indonesia is the duty of the Indonesian National Police. In carrying out the duties of the Indonesian National Police, assisted by Pam Swakarsa, who grew up in the community, has the task of securing areas and settlements, even now the organization's lifeline is developing, almost all require a Security Unit. Security guards have become a legitimate organization and have been recognized by the Government as a limited security personnel profession in carrying out their duties and roles as assistants to the function of the Police, as non-justice physical security to direct, prevent, crack down, and catch criminal acts that are caught in the sector of duty. The purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the implementation of the duties and roles of the Security Guard and identify and analyze the factors that hinder the Security Guard in the implementation of duties and roles in accordance with Perpolri No. 4 of 2020. The method that the author uses is a qualitative descriptive method. The data found in the field still has factors that need to be addressed, namely the direct implementation in the field starting from recruitment, training, and coaching security guards. The conclusion of this article contains how to carry out the duties and roles of security guards in accordance with Perpolri No. 4 of 2020 in the city of Surabaya.

Keywords: Security Guard, Duties and Roles, Perpolri No. 4 of 2020, Training.

A. Introduction

Foreign countries want to invest in Indonesia for bilateral and multilateral cooperation so that they are mutually beneficial to each other. One of the requirements that makes consideration on the part of a foreign State is the factor of homeland security to what extent its security. Because without a safe situation, it is impossible for cooperation transactions between countries to occur. The Indonesian government has an institution whose job is to maintain its security, namely the National Police of the Republic of Indonesia. The National Police has a very heavy task with such a large area with a population of 270.7 million people so large. We have had a self-defense security that is a Security Unit that grows up in the community tasked with securing an area or a settlement, even now it is developing in all lines of organizational life almost all require a security unit. With the existence of pengam a nan swakarsa has been inaugurated into a security unit by Mr.

Awaludin Jamin as a shah organization and has been recognized by the government as a limited security force in carrying out its duties and obligations as an auxiliary to the function of the police as a physical security non-justice to direct and prevent, crack down and arrest in

the event of a criminal act caught in the sector in which he is assigned. The question with the existence of the existing Security Unit is whether it is in accordance with expectations in carrying out its duties and roles based on the National Police regulation no. 4 of 2020, the author presents previous researchers ranging from recruitment, education and training, placement in jobs, observers as follows:

Rosida Dwi Fitriani (2017) Researching the Implementation (of Education and Training Program for Security Guards in Garda Total Security Yogyakarta. In the study, it was explained that the material in the training was in accordance with procedures and rules with no new findings for the innovation of training materials that had been determined from the center in this case from the National Police. The thing that needs to be deepened is that at the pre-education and training stage there is no material for the recruitment process, research when prospective security guards will enter education and training in accordance with the material that has been determined from the National Police, namely about psycho tests, only in formality because it is to meet the requirements.

Fery Syaputra (2014) Examining the problem D of the Work Contents of the Padang State University Security Unit, in the formulation of the problem it is said that the work discipline of security guard members in carrying out their duties is still lacking. This phenomenon is due to lack of discipline in complying with punctuality at work, lack of compliance with applicable regulations, lack of vigilance when carrying out duties and lack of a sense of responsibility, this is what makes the challenge in coaching in place work.

Journal of Security PT. Putra Tidar Perkasa Training Center (2018) Opening Training of Security Guard batch XXIX for 29 students in Batam city. In the research of educational results has produced several members of the Security Guard. In the process of accepting prospective members of the Security Guard has not implemented the complete requirements, namely the psycho test, the time allocated for the implementation of training education between theory and practice has not been fully implemented, in accordance with Perkapolri No. 18/2006 the allocation of time needed is 232 hours or 4 weeks for education Primary Mace training, but the reality time used is only 12 days. This will certainly affect the out put / quality of the training participants.

Mario Widiarto Sutantoputra (2020) in his notes and observations, that Perpol No. 4/2020 concerning Pam Swakarsa recorded 9 kinds of findings, describing the existence of new things considered to be legally awkward so as to cause unclear in understanding them.

Rafli Damar Bungsa Dewa, Nabila Indah Chairunnisa, Shofiyah Adila Farhana in their research discussed the Polemic of Reanimation of Swakarsa Security, the Dilemma Between

Community Policing and Vigilantism, the conclusion of the study is that the concept of Security Guard regulated in Perpol No. 4 Tahun 2020 is in accordance with the principle of community policing which involves the partnership of the swakarsa community to perform police duties with certain boundaries. It's just that refinement is still needed to avoid any abuse of power that leads to vigilantism. Regarding pam swakarsa from social institutions / local wisdom, the entire arrangement must be clarified starting from the definition of what is included in the social institutions that can be Pam Swakarsa, recruitment, training, to supervision and evaluation. This is to close any loopholes of vigilantism. In addition, there is a need for a proper supervision mechanism for the existence of Pam Swakarsa, so that if there are members of Pam Swakarsa who deviate from the implementation of their duties, the public can report it easily to law enforcement.

Teguh Husodo: In the regulation of the Chief of Police No. 4 of 2020, there is a change in the color of the security guard uniform, which was originally the color of the white shirt of dark blue pants to brown and the retirement age of the security guard. It is also mentioned that there are five types of security guard clothing including Daily Service Clothing (PDH), Special Field Service Clothing (PDL Sus), Field Service Clothing One (PDL One), Daily Civilian Clothing (PSH), and Complete Civilian Clothing (PSL). Each type of service clothing was distinguished between men and women either wearing a veil or not hooded. The uniforms of PDH, PDL Sus, and PDL One are all brown. In addition, the Perpol also arranged a security guard uniform hat for the PDH which is similar to the police. PDH is used for morning to evening tasks. The night officers all used PDL.. The next policy is retirement age. As stated in Article 31, the retirement age limit for security guards who come from individuals varies by class. For the implementing class, the retirement age is set at 56 years. For

supervisors it is set 58 years, and for managers 70 years. As for security guards who come from retired TNI or Polri, the retirement age is set at 60 years for the executor, 65 years for the supervisor, and 70 years for the manager. Teguh said that the implementation of the uniform was carried out in stages, starting in January 2021 and was targeted to be fully implemented in February 2021.

Andita Rahma: Security Guard Rank and How to Get. In Article 19, it is stated that if there are three levels of security guard members, namely manager, supervisor, and executor." The rank of manager as referred to in Article 19 letter a, includes the rank of the main manager; associate manager; and managers. Then, for the rank of supervisor, it includes the rank of the main supervisor; Associate supervisor and supervisor. Finally, for the rank of executor, it includes the rank of the main executor, intermediate executor and executor," reads Article 20

in the PerPol, on Wednesday, September 16, 2020. To get the rank, a security guard must first attend training, namely primary mace training for the executive level, intermediate mace training for the supervisor level and main mace training for the manager level. The training should only be organized by the National Police and BUJP which have SIO training services. Furthermore, the promotion for per-level rank of manager based on the earliest service period is per-two years. The details are, from manager to associate manager can be implemented within a period after one year of service as a manager and pass the main mace level competency test. Then, from the associate manager to the main manager, they must meet the requirements, namely proposed by security guard service users based on needs and pass the main mace competency test. Then, the promotion for each rank of supervisor is based on the period of service as early as per four years. The details are from supervisor to associate supervisor, can be carried out within a period of time after two years of service as a supervisor and pass the intermediate mace level competency test. Furthermore, from associate supervisors to managers, they must meet the requirements, namely the needs of security guard service users, pass the intermediate mace level competency test, have special skills, and pass the main mace training. Finally, the promotion to the rank of executor is based on the period of service as early as per four years. The details are, from executor to intermediate executor can be carried out within a period of time after two years of service and pass the G level competency test there is Pratama. Then, from the intermediate implementer to the supervisor, they must meet the requirements,

namely the needs of security guard service users, pass the primary mace level competency test, have special skills, and pass intermediate mace training. Azis Said: Stating that Perpol No. 4 of 2020 concerning Pam Swakarsa Efforts to Reform Security Guard Breeding. "Perpol No. 4 of 2020 is considered as the foundation of security guard reform in Indonesia, considering that security guards will become a profession, which has a career path based on competence and length of service," said Chairman of the DPP of the Indonesian Security Guard Professional Association (APSI), Azis Said during the National Meeting in Bandung, Monday (02/11). In Perpol No. 4 of 2020, many things regarding security guard regulations have changed compared to the regulation of the Chief of Police (Perkap) No. 24 of 2007, namely about the definition of security guards, recruitment, employment status, career path, uniform clothing, associations, etc., have changed. "APSI as an association in the field of security registered in Baharkam Polri which is involved in the formulation of Perpol No. 4 Tahun 2020, needs to explain to the public and stakeholders in the security sector, about these changes. " he said. " For APSI, this step is in an effort to advance Industrial Security in Indonesia in general and the breeding of the Security Guard profession in particular. APSI

hopes that with the existence of Perpol Pamswakarsa, companies that use Security Guard services, Security Service Business Entities, Security Guards, Satkamling and the public to understand and comply with Perpol No. 4 ToF 2020 in carrying out security in their respective areas. He explained that there are six important changes in Perpol No. 4 of 2020, including, First, security guards have been distinguished from satkamling. Security guard is a unit or professional group carrying out non-judicial limited police functions that are recruited according to the provisions of the National Police, trained in security guard education and have a member identity card (KTA) and have employment status (P origin 1 verses 3 and 4). so security guards are currently considered a profession where before carrying out duties, they must have passed the mandatory training G ada P ratama / G ada Madya or G ada Utama (Porigin 10). Secondly, Recruitment should only be done by Badan Usaha Jasa P engamanan (BUJP), and users of security guard services or companies (article 8). so the recruitment of security guards is only done by the company. if individuals want to use the services of security guards at home, please get in touch with BUJP because they are not allowed to recruit themselves. Third, All security guards must have employment status, whether with sistem Perjanjian Kerja Waktu Tertentu (PKWT) or as a permanent employee of the

company. This is intended so that- the labor rights of security guards can be fulfilled by BUJP or companies, in accordance with laws and regulations (Porigin 1 paragraph 4). So from now on there are no more security guards who are given wages under the UMP and do not have BPJS and other rights. This is an old struggle and obsession of APSI which has now been accommodated in Perpol No 4 Tahun 2020. Fourth, Security guard members have a rank group, namely the executor of the security guard, the supervisor of the security guard and the manager of the security guard. Each rank group will have 3 ranks (Porigin 19). Thus, security guards from now on will have a rank and rank based on their competence and length of service. This is a form of security guard breeding. Fifth, the security guard's uniform changed its color to brown similar to the Police uniform with a gradation 20% younger than the police uniform in addition to creating a "new image" for the security guard corps, also to be different from the Satkamling uniform. The implementation of the uniform color change is given one year (Porigin 45), considering that BUJP or the company annually provides new clothing rations for its security guards. So it doesn't cause a new cost burden, but just changes its color. It is expected that on 5 Agustus 2021 all security guards in Indonesia who have met the requirements as security guards, have changed into brown uniforms. Fifth, the security guard's uniform changed its color to brown similar to the Police uniform with a gradation 20% younger than the police uniform in addition to creating a "new image" for the security guard corps, also

to be different from the Satkamling uniform. The implementation of the uniform color change is given one year (Porigin 45), considering that BUJP or the company annually provides new clothing rations for its security guards. So it doesn't cause a new cost burden, but just changes its color. It is expected that on 5 Agustus 2021 all security guards in Indonesia who have met the requirements as security guards, have changed into brown uniforms.

On this paper researchers explore the extent of the level of competence of members of the security unit in carrying out their duties and roles based on Perpol No 4 of 2020. with the intention of providing input to the leadership of the National Police so that there is a significant increase in the level of competence of members of the security unit. The scope of this research is limited to those related to security units with research objects in the city of Surabaya.

To find out the competence of security unit officers, one of them must explore, how the Security Service Provider Business Entity in recruiting and equipping Security Guard training, How to maintain optimal competence, how to keep its level of

discipline well maintained, the level of welfare including salary every month and the coaching system a, his at work as a security guard officer. By knowing these problems, the level of Satpam's ability to carry out his duties and roles in the field will be found. How is the operational realization of Perpol No 4 Year 2020 in the field ?

B. Methods

Data collection in qualitative research is carried out in natural conditions (natural setting). Data collection and data processing techniques in qualitative research are mostly carried out by: observation, interviews, questionnaires and documentation (Sugiyono.2014: 223) Observation can be carried out directly by visiting the location and observing, then recording the results of these observations and documented as a result of observation. Observation can also be done indirectly by listening to the explanations or stories of the sources.

Interview, Meet the head / director / manager of the agency, company, the purpose of obtaining data on research materials, after receiving recommendations, then ask for the data that the author needs by meeting Human Resources Development (HRD) and its staff and meeting in a manner directly by random sample to the head of the security guard, as well as the supervisor/head of the squad, as well as the members by sampling at the workplace who is performing the task. Based on the data obtained, the author can analyze by being faced with a reality that is directly found that will produce a conclusion in his sector.

Questionnaire/questioner, questionnaire/questionnaire method is a data collection technique carried out by providing a set of questions or written statements to respondents for questioning.

Documentation, , The documentation method is a record of past events that can take the form of writings, drawings, or monumental works of a person (Sugiyono, 2014: 240). The documentation method is one of the methods of collecting qualitative data by viewing or analyzing documents created by the subject himself or by others by the subject. Documentation is one of the ways that qualitative researchers can do to get an overview from the subject's point of view through a written media and other documentation written or made directly by the subject concerned (Herdiansyah, 2010).

C. Results and Discussion

Perpol No. 4 years 2020 by APSI is considered as the foundation of security guard reform in Indonesia, considering that security guards will become a profession, which has a career path based on competence and length of service, as conveyed by the general chairman of the DPP Apsi Azis Said during the national meeting in Bandung, in Perpol no. 4 of 2020 many things regarding the management of security guards have changed when compared to the regulation of the Chief of Police no. 24 of 2007, That is, the understanding of recruitment security guards, employment status, career path, uniform clothing, associations and others has changed. Apsi as an association in the field of security registered in the Baharkam Polri, which is involved in the formulation of Perpolri no. 4 of 2020 needs to explain to the public and stakeholders in the field of security, about these changes. For Apsi, the steps are in an effort to advance the Security Industry in Indonesia in general and the breeding of the Security Guard profession in particular. Apsi hopes that with the existence of Perpol Pam, companies that use security services for Security Guards, Security Services Business Entities, Security Guards, Satkamling and the public will understand and comply with Perpol No. 4 of 2020 in carrying out security in their respective areas.

Implications of BUJP The training time used by Security Guard Education is only 2 weeks, in accordance with the provisions of the National Police the allocation of time for Gada Pratama security guard training education is 4/5 weeks, Student results or out put student results caused by the length of time in education according to the author that students entering the dormitory will meet with friends who come from various regions and backgrounds. In education, the participants in addition to receiving the main teaching material as Security Guards will also receive material about mentality, spirit and spirit as well as esprit de corps as

members of the Security Guard. Related to that, the time factor used will affect the attitude, mentality and sense of pride even though this is relative, because it depends on the individual the extent of his absorption in receiving lessons. In education, participants in receiving teaching materials certainly expend energy, thoughts feeling even full concentration and excellent health conditions, this will show the results of their education and some even feel heavy during education but some also feel not heavy.

In Perpolri no. 4 of 2020, the existence of a rank for security guards, the author argues that the policy is not appropriate because of the rank, the security guard needs an organization that manages the security guard members when in fact the Security Guard is a self-help security unit, meaning that the existence of the security guard member arises from the will, awareness and for the benefit of the community then obtains confirmation from the National Police and is trusted by the community not the government.

D. Conclusion

Based on the results of theoretical research and findings in the field starting from the central level of policy makers, the regional level, the implementing level of the public policy and its implementation as a member of the security unit, the author can provide a conclusion and factors that hinder the implementation of Perpolri no. 4 of 2020. as follows : Perpolri No. 4 of 2020 is a central-level public policy that makes the source of the entire series of self-defense security activities in which there is a security unit, the contents of the Perpolri after being studied are still partly using other Perkapolri :

1. The implementer of public policy perpolri 4 of 2020 in the regions is the East Java Regional Police in this case the Dirbinmas based on the findings in the field has carried out supervision and evaluation of the extent to which security guards in the East Java region, especially Surabaya, in carrying out their duties and roles, through audits at BUJP and direct monitoring in the field but there are still many who have not getting attention or actions such as uniform clothes for security guards brown color is widely used by those who are not entitled to wear.
2. The Security Service Business Entity that is responsible for fostering security guard members, based on the findings in the field there are still many security guard members in carrying out their duties have not been able to show the expected professional level, including the Security Services Business Entity that has obtained an Operational permit to carry out education and training based on the findings in the field there are still the

results of their education have not shown a professional level and adequate competence has also not implemented the guidelines or instructions from the Police Department regarding the allocation of time for primary mace training for only 2 weeks and the recruitment of security guards is partial without going through psychological tests.

3. From the user or user of the Security Unit personnel who are responsible for problems, facilities and infrastructure for security guards, including providing guidance and welfare in the form of salary findings in the field there are still many security guard users / users providing salaries still below the MSE. As found in the field, it turns out that there are still users or users of security guards who have not met the basic needs of security guard members, which will eventually affect the professional level as security guard members.
4. Security guard members on duty at work have generally carried out their duties well, but there are still findings in the field that do not show a less friendly, polite, polite and responsive appearance and attitude in providing services to guests / others.
5. The hope in the future for security guard members is those who have a soul as guided by the code of ethics, guides and promises of security guards that have been accepted as guidelines in carrying out daily duties Based on the results of the research as a whole and the conclusions obtained, several suggestions can be developed for interested parties in this research. The suggestions put forward are as follows:
6. After exploring the contents of Perpolri no. 4 of 2020 concerning Self-Defense Security and its implementation and implementation, it is still necessary to improve several provisions, including the material provided to recruit Gada Pratama about the appropriate and effective allocation of time associated with the results of security guard education to face tasks in such a complex field.
7. To the Security Services Business Entity that has obtained an Operation Permit, the training needs and must remain guided by the applicable provisions under Perpolri no. 4 of 2020, including prospective training participants must go through psychotest, the time used for primary mace teaching material is 232 hours within 5 weeks , however, the time used by BUJP is only 2 weeks, for this reason, it is recommended that there be consideration and review and policies from the leadership of the Police Headquarters.
8. There is input from various communities about the brown security guard uniforms which confuse which are Police and which are Security Guards, for this reason, it is recommended that there be an immediate decision from the leadership of the National Police starting when the security guard uniforms as a substitute will come into effect.

4.9 The existence of the rank of security guard in perpolri no. 4 of 2020 which until now has not been implemented according to the author is the right decision, because of the rank, the security guard is a permanent employee, when in fact in the field the security guard members are most of the contract employees (certain time work agreements). It is suggested that the rank in the security guard needs to be reviewed or cancelled.

E. References

- Andita Rahma (2020, September) Kepangkatan Satpam dan Cara Mendapatkannya. Tempo.co. Diperoleh dari : <https://nasional.tempo.co/read/1386803/3-kepangkatan-satpam-dan-cara-mendapatkannya>
- Ayu Agustia(2018) Journal Penelitian Kepuasan Kerja Satpam Universitas Pajajaran ditinjau dari aspek Job Discription Index (hlm. 71-76)
- Azis Said (2020, November) Perpol Pam Swakarsa Upaya Reformasi Pemuliaaan Satpam. Media Indonesia. <https://mediaindonesia.com/politik-dan-hukum/357685/perpol-pam-swakarsa-upaya-reformasi-pemuliaaan-satpam>
- Burhan. B(2013). Penelitian Kualitatif Komunikasi,Ekonomi,Kebijakan. Publik, dan Ilmu Sosial lainnya Jakarta: Prenada Media Group.
- Burhan Bungin, Agus Sukristyanto, V. Rudy Handoko. Buku Pedoman Penulisan Mkpdp, Proposal dan Disertasi Program Studi Doktor Ilmu Adminitrasi Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya.
- Creswel. J.W (2014) Research Design Qualitative.Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches(4 ed). Thousand Oaks.CA Sage.
- Dunn, William N(2000). Analisis kebijakan Publik. Yogyakarta : Gajah Mada University Press.
- Fery Syaputra (2014) Journal penelitian disiplin Kerja Satpam Universitas Negeri Padang. Diperoleh dari <http://repository.unp.ac.id/11443/>
- Heru Susetyo (2008) Journal Penelitian menuju Paradigma Keamanan Komprehensif berperspektif keamanan Manusia dalam kebijakan keamanan Nasional Indonesia. (hlm 1-10)
- Jurnal Security PT Putra Tidar Perkasa Training Center (2017) , membuka Pendidikan dan Pembentukan (Diktuk) Satpam angkatan angkatan XXXIII untuk 63 siswa, diakses dari <https://jurnalsecurity.com/label/putra-tidar-perkasa/>
- Jurnal Security Polres Sorong (2020) dalam rangka Meningkatkan Kompetensi dan kemampuan 59 Peserta Stapam Mengikuti Pelatihan dan Pendidikan Gada Prtama yang dilaksanakan oleh PT PKKS.
- Mario Widiarto Sutantoputra (2020) catatan atas Perpol No 04 Tahun2020 tentang Pam Swakarsa.

- Margaret, Rahmad Budiono(2014) Journal Penelitian Satpam sebagai pekerja, dalam hukum Positip Indonesia
- Noto Susanto (2021, Januari 2021) : Implementasi Turjawali Untuk Satpam. Kompasiana. Diperoleh dari <https://www.kompasiana.com/noto69047/5ff0669dd541df7a553a1409/implementasi-turjawali-untuk-satpam>
- Peraturan Kepala Kepolisian Negara Republik Indonesia nomor 24 tahun 2007 tanggal 10 Desember 2007 Tentang Sistem Managemen Pengamnan Organisasi, perusahaan dan/atau instansi/ lembaga pemerintah.
- Peraturan Kepolisian Republik Indonesia No 04 tahun 2020 tentang Pam Swakarsa
- PP No. 43 Tahun 2012 tentang tata cara pelaksanaan koordinasi, pengawasan dan pembinaan teknis terhadap kepolisian khusus, penyidik pegawai negeri sipil dan bentuk-bentuk pengamanan swakarsa,
- R`afi Damar Bungsa Dewo, Nabila Indah Chairunnisa, Shofiyah Adila Farhana : Polemik Penghidupan Kembali Pengamanan Swakarsa, Dilema Antara Community Policing Dan Vigilantisme. Diperoleh dari <https://jurnal.dpr.go.id/index.php/politica/article/view/2148>
- Rifky Aditya (2015) Jurnal Pengaruh Pelatihan terhadap Kompetensi dan Kinerja Karyawan, diakses dari <https://www.neliti.com/id/publications/86363/pengaruh-pelatihan-terhadap-kompetensi-dan-kinerja-karyawan-studi-pada-karyawan>
- Rosida Dwi Fitriani(2017) Journal penelitian Program pendidikan dan Pelatihan Satpam. Di peroleh dari <https://journal.student.uny.ac.id/index.php/pls/index>
- Security Tidar Perkasa Training Center (2018). Diperoleh dari <https://putratidarperkasa.com/ptp-training-center-kembali-buka-pendidikan-gada-pratama-angkatan-xxviii-tahun-2018/pelatihan-satpam-security-gada-pratama-angkatan-28-penyematan-pita/>
- Soleman B Ponto (2020) perpol 4/2020, Polemik & Kontroversi Pamswakarsa. Gatra News. Diperoleh dari <https://www.gatra.com/news-490657-politik-perpol-42020-polemik-dan-kontroversi-pamswakarsa.html>
- Sudahnann (2011) Kewenangan Satpam sebagai tenaga keamanan di Perusahaan. (hlm. 140-148). Diperoleh dari <https://ejournal.uwks.ac.id/myfiles/201207081310382587/11.pdf>
- Teguh Husodo : Terapkan Peraturan Kapolri No 4 Tahun 2020 Warna Seragam Satpam menjadi Cokelat dan usia pension Satpam. Universitas Padjajaran. Diperoleh dari <https://www.unpad.ac.id/2021/01/terapkan-peraturan-kapolri-unpad-ubah-warna-seragam-satpam-menjadi-cokelat/>